

SPEECH THERAPY RHYTHMICITY AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL FOR CORRECTIVE INTERVENTION IN CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237576>

Abstract. *This article explores the potential of speech therapy rhythmicity in working with children who have speech disorders. It presents various methods of speech therapy rhythmicity, the structure of logorhythmic sessions, and offers a contemporary perspective on optimizing the implementation of logorhythmic activities for children with speech impairments.*

Keywords: *speech disorders, speech therapy rhythmicity, logorhythmic exercise, speech, music and movement.*

In today's rapidly changing world of advanced IT technologies, characterized by a plethora of gadgets offering a wide range of entertainment options that do not require personal interaction, physical engagement, mental effort, or intellectual exertion, the issue of speech development and communication skills in children has become increasingly evident and relevant. The 2020 pandemic once again confirms the position of A. R. Luria on the relationship between the speech function and other higher mental functions [11] and the unity of the patterns of the formation of thinking and speech within the framework of the psychology of cognitive processes of L. S. Vygotsky [9]. A. N. Leontiev argues that the word, verbal communication and joint activities with other people have a regulating function of behavior [12]. Forced isolation, excessive presence of television, computer and the Internet, lack of communication in the family and general deterioration of health have led to a whole generation of children with speech disorders, problems with cognitive processes, behavior regulation and the emotional-volitional sphere.

One of the goals of our research is to study literary sources devoted to the history and scientific and methodological foundations of speech therapy rhythms, practical experiments and theoretical conclusions, in order to clarify the prerequisites for the emergence of this direction in special pedagogy and have information on modern trends in the development of methods and means of speech therapy rhythms.

The study sets the task, based on the methodological developments of domestic and foreign authors, to find out the relevance and availability of speech therapy rhythm tools, their beneficial effect on the physiological and psycho-speech development of children.

The modern scientific and methodological basis of special pedagogy allows us to very accurately and promptly diagnose and correct the most complex speech disorders, carry out preventive measures in order to prevent the development of speech deficiency, carry out early intervention in the disharmonious development of the child, deal with issues of education, training and correction at any age stage. And one of the effective ways to overcome speech disorders is the use of methods and tools of speech therapy rhythm.

It is crucial to understand that logopedic rhythmicity is a method of correcting speech underdevelopment that affects speech and non-speech disorders using a system of exercises that

implement the connection between speech, music and movement. Having emerged at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries as a science of rhythmic education of students thanks to the Swiss musician, composer and teacher E. Jacques-Dalcroze (1865-1950), having been successfully implemented as therapeutic rhythmic in the system of hospital rehabilitation, logopedic rhythmic was transformed into a system of corrective action of special pedagogy, including speech therapy. Until the 1980s, logorhythmics was mainly used in work with stutterers and patients with aphasia [14] [7]. G. A. Volkova developed methodological recommendations for the use of logorhythmic exercises in corrective speech therapy work. Researchers such as R. L. Babushkina [3], G. R. Shashkina [15], G. I. Anisimova [1], E. S. Anishchenkova [2] and others systematized and supplemented the developments of G. A. Volkova, taking into account changes in the style and nature of the learning process and the expansion of the possibilities of corrective action in various nosologies of speech disorders in children.

Music has an undoubted positive effect on the development of the human psyche. In addition to aesthetic education, music also affects the emotional state, promotes behavior regulation, develops memory, attention and imagination, improves the psychophysical state [13]. Rhythm, as one of the key concepts of musical science, is important both as a global phenomenon (change of seasons, days of the week, alternation of day and night, switching of traffic light colors, alternation of lessons and breaks at school, etc.) and as a narrow concept (rhythm of a musical piece, rhythmization of speech, stress in a word, intonation stress in a sentence, rhythm of a poem, etc.) [10]. With the help of musical rhythmic exercises, work is carried out on breathing, prosody and intonation, the tempo and fluency of speech are normalized, attention and memory are developed. The rhythmic component of music helps to balance the activity of the child's nervous system [4] [5].

In the context of Bulgarian scientists L. Bonev, P. Slynchev, St. Bankov wrote about a special system of physical exercises to music that develops a sense of rhythm and is used for corrective and health purposes - "kinesitherapy". [6]

This topic holds great significance because movement exercises are an integral part of logorhythmic classes. In addition to developing coordination, attention, spatial thinking, improving physical condition and muscle tone, motor exercises contribute to the development of speech activity, since speech is directly related to movement. The rhythm of movements performed to music contributes to the organization and fluency of speech of stutterers, and has a beneficial effect on the rate of speech in bradylalia and tachylalia. Work on physiological and phonatory breathing helps improve prosody in rhinolalia and dysarthria.

Understanding this issue is essential for speech as verbal instruction, pronunciation, singing or melody recitation should be included in the lesson everywhere. This can be either an articulation exercise and singing vowels, or performing favorite songs and telling about impressions after listening to a musical excerpt. Depending on the pedagogical task, the speech therapist prepares certain verbal material for the lesson.

G. A. Volkova suggests the following lesson structure [8]:

1. Introductory part, musical and rhythmic warm-up, including formation, greeting, telling children the general topic of the lesson, breathing and motor exercises to music and counting.

2. The main part, which is aimed at overcoming the leading speech disorder. Depending on the need, this includes breathing and voice exercises, articulatory gymnastics with facial exercises, singing, melodeclamation, etc.

3. The motor part with exercises for movement, displacement and rebuilding, dance elements are included, the tempo and rhythm of movements are worked out.

4. The final part, the purpose of which is to normalize breathing, calm the heart rate and relieve emotional tension. Various relaxation exercises are used in this part.

The main methods and means of speech therapy rhythm are:

- Walking and marching in different directions
- Exercises for the development of breathing, voice and articulation
- Exercises regulating muscle tone
- Exercises activating attention
- Speech exercises without musical accompaniment
- Exercises for developing a sense of musical size or meter
- Exercises for developing a sense of musical tempo
- Rhythmic exercises
- Singing
- Exercises in playing instruments
- Independent musical activity
- Play activity
- Exercises for developing creative initiative
- Final exercises
- Visual, verbal and practical teaching methods

G. R. Shashkina [15] from the speech therapy rhythm described by G. A. Volkova [8] separately identifies exercises for the development of fine motor skills and exercises with elements of dance from the section of musical and motor means, as well as exercises for the development of phonation breathing, exercises for the development of speech attention, exercises with objects and speech exercises (melodeclamation) from the section of motor and speech tools.

To put this into perspective speech therapy rhythm remains a relevant means of correctional work with children with speech disorders due to the wide opportunities for a creative and imaginative approach to classes, a “departure” from traditional, conservative methods, which, without a doubt, bring results, but often do not take into account the characteristic features of a modern child, his satiety with toys and “motivators”, accessibility to entertainment content. A child of the 21st century can visit any country in the world without reading books and without leaving his room, live communication has found a replacement in correspondence on social networks and messengers, emotional expression of feelings in words has been replaced by “emoji”, reading aloud is not relevant due to artificial intelligence. As a result, the so-called “digital” autism has arisen.

A significant challenge faced today is the musical component of speech therapy rhythm is interesting for children, since it is a means of creative self-expression of the child. Even when directed by a teacher, musical activity brings joy and pleasure. Children like to play musical instruments themselves, compare their sounds, listen to music, sing songs, learn dances and do exercises with musical accompaniment. Along with modeling, drawing and designing, speech therapy rhythms provide scope for the child's creative freedom.

In the context of up to a certain time, one of the conditions for conducting a successful logorhythmic lesson was the presence of three specialists: a speech therapist, a teacher and a music director. The pedagogical and correctional focus, competent selection of musical material, and

correct execution of exercises according to verbal instructions depended on their interaction. Today, thanks to information accessibility, digitalization of the educational process and progressive equipment, a speech therapist-defectologist, with appropriate training, using computer programs, is able to conduct a lesson alone. Innovative technologies allow a specialist to control the course of the lesson, promptly reproduce the necessary audio and video material, pause, speed up or slow down the execution of the task if necessary.

Taking into account the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. The development of speech function and other higher mental functions are interdependent. Underdevelopment of speech affects cognitive functions, leads to problems in behavior, self-regulation and disorders in the emotional-volitional sphere.

2. The means and methods of speech therapy rhythms provide an opportunity to fully carry out corrective work with children with speech disorders, including: work on breathing, pronunciation, gross and fine motor skills, phonemic perception, sound analysis and synthesis, etc. During speech therapy rhythm classes, vocabulary expands, phonemic hearing and prosody improve, and speech and non-speech processes become rhythmic.

3. Speech therapy rhythms is a relevant method of corrective influence, especially since innovative technologies make it possible to facilitate and optimize the preparation and conduct of the lesson.

However, there remains a concern regarding. statistics show that every year the number of children with speech disorders of varying complexity is growing. There is also a growing need for innovative, advanced, original approaches to educational, pedagogical and correctional work with such children. Speech therapy rhythm combines traditional methods of correctional intervention and a combination of art therapy, music therapy and dance movement therapy, which makes it especially attractive, accessible and expands the creative potential of specialists and children.

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